

ISic1535

I.Sicily inscription 1535

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 37208

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Ἐνθάδε κῆτε Ἀριάγνη □
2. μόνανδρος τελευτᾷ
3. ἐτῶν ἑβδομήκοντα πέντε ὁ δὲ
4. Θεὸς κὲ ὁ Χρισ[τ]ὸς αὐτο[ῦσιὸςκὲτὸ]
5. Ἅγιον Πνεῦμα[αἰεῖξῶναμετατῶνἀγίων]
6. αὐτῆς τὸ ψυ[χίδιονἘκοιμήθητῆ]
7. ἦρ(ὸ) ιε · καλ(ανδῶν) · Ὀκ[τωβρίων]

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953 with changes based on Orsi's edition (1923)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645034

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0015

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.41

Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At 117 no.14

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